

THE MODERATING ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL IMAGINATIVENESS IN THE TRANSITION FROM OPPORTUNITY RECOGNITION TO ENTREPRENEURIAL ACTION

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PURPOSE/PROBLEM

Central to entrepreneurship is not whether objective and observable opportunities exist independently of individuals, but rather, whether individuals perceive opportunities and act upon them (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006). The ability to recognize opportunity is manifested in the concept of entrepreneurial alertness which is defined as the ability of a person to identify new opportunities that are often overlooked by others (Kerzner, 1979). However, there are mixed results supporting the transition from opportunity recognition to entrepreneurial action (Neneh, 2019). Therefore, it is argued that the journey should be influenced by contingent factors.

A great number of previous studies have investigated the impacts of tangible resources such as capital, assets, venture teams or traditional resources such as experience, knowledge, motivation, etc. However, little empirical studies have been conducted to investigate the role of imagination although it plays a very important role in envisioning the new venture (Kier & McMullen, 2018). This problem was caused by the lack of a measurement scale for this concept. Based on the theory of creative problem solving, Kier and McMullen (2018) developed a measurement scale for entrepreneurial imaginativeness which is conceptualized as a cognitive ability that combines the ability of imagination with the knowledge needed to mentally simulate various task-related scenarios in entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial imaginativeness is classified into three distinct domains including creative imaginativeness, social imaginativeness and practical imaginativeness which vary

across individuals and predict ideation quantity and quality over and above experience, knowledge and motivation (McMullen & Kier, 2017). McMullen et al. (2021) suggested that more empirical studies should be conducted to investigate the role of entrepreneurial imaginativeness on entrepreneurial action. However, to our understanding, there have been no empirical studies investigating the moderating role of this concept on the transition from opportunity identification to entrepreneurial action.

In sum, to fill the above-mentioned gaps, we will investigate the moderating role of entrepreneurial imaginativeness on the transition from opportunity recognition to entrepreneurial intention and behaviour. Specifically, we will empirically test the moderating impact of creative imaginativeness and social imaginativeness on the relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and entrepreneurial intention and the moderating impact of practical imaginativeness on the relationship between entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial behaviour. In doing so, we make another attempt to prove the important role of imagination in entrepreneurship literature which is calling for more empirical investigation. In addition, the study tries to explain the mechanism fostering the journey of venture creation which definitely involves uncertainty.

ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOUR

Entrepreneurial intention (EI) refers to an individual's commitment towards starting a new business (Kruguer, 1993). Because entrepreneurial behaviour (EB) is widely viewed as an intentional behaviour rather than a spontaneous one, EI is posited as a strong determinant of EB which is defined as the 'discovery, evaluation and exploitation of an opportunity' (Shane & Vankataraman, 2000). EB represents the index reflecting the scope of start-up activities that an individual has already carried out on his or her way to the new venture creation (Shirokova et al., 2016).

ENTREPRENEURIAL ALERTNESS

Kirzner (1979, 1999) argued that entrepreneurs were those who alertly noticed or discovered market errors and took advantages of those discoveries to systematically nudge the market to the equilibrium. Alertness has played a central role in entrepreneurial opportunity discovery (Tang et al., 2012). Alert individuals have been described as those who have an "antenna" that permits gaps recognition with limited clues (Kirzner, 1979), or have a 'unique preparedness' to consistently scan the environment for opportunities (Kaish & Gilad, 1991).

Based on Kirzner (1979) and McMullen and Shepherd (2006), Tang et al. (2012) conceptualized alertness as having three complementary dimensions: scanning and searching for new information, connecting previously-desperate information,

and evaluating whether the new information represents an opportunity. Accordingly, entrepreneurial alertness is operationalized as a second-order formative constructs including three dimensions as: alert scanning and search, alert association and connection, and alert evaluation and judgement. First, alert scanning and search dimension allows individuals to build a vast array of domain-relevant information constituting ones' sensory store which then helps to facilitate the integration and accumulation of new knowledge. Second, alert association and connection dimension enables individuals to connect different ideas to form new ideas. Third, evaluation and judgment dimension help individuals to choose the best opportunities.

ENTREPRENEURIAL IMAGINATIVENESS

Entrepreneurship is viewed as a function of innovation (Schumpeter, 1942), communication (McMullen, 2015), and administration (Wagner, 2003; McMullen & Shepherd, 2006). Following this mainstream, Kier and McMullen (2018) operationalized entrepreneurial imaginativeness as a cognitive skill that combines the ability of imagination with the knowledge needed to mentally simulate various task-related scenarios in entrepreneurship including innovation, communication and administration. With innovation function, entrepreneurs use their creative imaginativeness to envision something that cannot be or is not currently being observed for the purposes of novel, original, artistic, or innovative creation. With communication function, social imaginativeness is used to envision something that cannot be or is not currently being observed for the purposes of taking the perspective of others, seeing and feeling the world from another's frame of reference, or reading the desires, intentions, beliefs, and emotions of others. Lastly, practical imaginativeness can help entrepreneurs to envision something that cannot be or is not currently being observed for the purposes of planning, organizing, analysing, or managing information, resources, or projects. The three imaginativeness skills vary across individuals (McMullen and Kier, 2017) and they predict new venture idea quantity and quality differently over and above the effects of motivation, knowledge, and experience (Kier and McMullen, 2018).

HYPOTHESIS AND MODEL

ENTREPRENEURIAL ALERTNESS, ENTREPRENEURIAL INTENTION AND ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOUR

Alertness has played a central role in entrepreneurial opportunity discovery (Tang et al., 2012). With the ability to identify new opportunities overlooked by others, an individual is more likely to have the intention to exploit that opportunity. Kirzner (1979, 1999) argued that entrepreneurs were those who alertly noticed or

discovered market errors and took advantages of those discoveries to systematically nudge the market to the equilibrium. Some previous studies have supported the positive relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and entrepreneurial intention (Van et al., 2008; Hu et al., 2018; Neneh, 2019; Gill et al., 2021).

The theory of planned behaviour (Ajzen, 1991) posited that individual behaviour is predicted by his/her intention which is influenced by attitudes, subjective norm and behavioural control. Since entrepreneurial behaviour (EB) is widely viewed as an intentional behaviour rather than a spontaneous one, EI is suggested as a strong determinant of EB which is defined as the ‘discovery, evaluation and exploitation of an opportunity’ (Shane & Vankataraman, 2000). Previous studies have showed that EI positively related to EB (Shirokova et al, 2016; Neneh, 2019). As a result, it is hypothesized that:

H1: entrepreneurial intention mediates the relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and entrepreneurial behaviour.

THE MODERATING ROLE OF ENTREPRENEURIAL IMAGINATIVENESS IN THE TRANSITION FROM ENTREPRENEURIAL ALERTNESS TO ENTREPRENEURIAL BEHAVIOUR

Entrepreneurs are those who respond to and create change through their entrepreneurial actions which refers to behaviours in response to a judgmental decision under uncertainty about a possible opportunity for profit (McMullen et al., 2006). Operating under uncertainty, entrepreneurs must rely on their mental simulation to envision every task-related scenario in their entrepreneurial journey (Kier & McMullen, 2018). Besides, Kirzner (1999) posited that entrepreneurial alertness in single-period case can best discover overlooked opportunities, but in multi-period case, it must be accompanied by the entrepreneur’s perception of the way in which creative and imaginative action may vitally shape the kind of transactions that will be entered into in the future market periods (Kirzner, 1999). As a result, the entrepreneurs’ latent ability of imagination which manifested in entrepreneurial imaginativeness is believed to moderate the transition from opportunity recognition and entrepreneurial action.

First, individuals with strong creative imaginativeness envision something that cannot be or is not currently being observed for the purposes of novel, original, artistic, or innovative creation (Kier & McMullen, 2018). As such, the more vivid the identified opportunity is, the more likely the individual desire to start the new venture. It is therefore hypothesized that:

H2: Creative imaginativeness moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and entrepreneurial intention.

Second, upon recognizing the opportunity, individuals of high social imaginativeness who can see and feel the world of the prospective actors in the new venture creation journey will be more likely to have a stronger intention towards creating new venture. It is therefore hypothesized that:

H3: Social imaginativeness moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial alertness and entrepreneurial intention.

Third, individuals who are high in practical imaginativeness can envision something that cannot be or is not currently being observed for the purposes of planning, organizing, analysing, or managing information, resources, or projects (Kier & McMullen, 2018). If individual can clearly see how they can administer their future venture, they will take actions to actualize their venture creation. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H4: Practical imaginativeness moderates the relationship between entrepreneurial intention and entrepreneurial behaviour.

In sum, the proposed research model is illustrated in figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model

MEASUREMENT SCALES

The measurement scales for entrepreneurial imaginativeness are adopted from Kier & McMullen (2018). Entrepreneurial alertness is measured by 13 items borrowed from Tang et al. (2012). Entrepreneurial intention is measured by 6 items adopted from Shirokova et al. (2016). The 5-point Likert which anchored from Strongly disagree to Strongly agree is used for creative imaginativeness, social

imaginativeness, practical imaginativeness, entrepreneurial alertness, and entrepreneurial intention. Because entrepreneurial behavior represents the index reflecting the scope of start-up activities that an individual has already carried out on his or her way to the new venture creation (Shirokova et al., 2016), it is measured on a scale from 0 (no activities) to 1 (full engagement in all listed start-up activities). The listed activities are adopted from Shirokova et al. (2016). All the items are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Measurement scales

Constructs	Measurement items	Source
Creative Imaginativeness (5-point Likert)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I consider myself to be inventive 2. I consider myself to be innovative 3. I demonstrate originality in my work 4. I like to create original work 5. People say that I am artistic 6. Being creative is a large part of who I am 	Kier & McMullen (2018)
Social imaginativeness	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It is easy for me to see things from the other person's point of view 2. I always make an effort to see the world through other people's eyes 3. It is easy for me to understand why people feel the way they do 4. I have a good sense for what other people are feeling 5. I can read people's emotions just from their facial expressions 6. I am good at reading people 	
Practical Imaginativeness (5-point Likert)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I tend to be good at project management 2. I can picture what the bottleneck of a system will be 3. Before I face a new situation, I picture the issues I may encounter and plan accordingly 4. I see connections between seemingly unrelated pieces of information 5. Forming mental images helps me solve problems 6. I extrapolate existing methods to solve new problems 	

Entrepreneurial alertness (5-point Likert)	Scanning and search	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I have frequent interactions with others to acquire new information. 2. I always keep an eye out for new business ideas when looking for information. 3. I read news, magazines, or trade publications regularly to acquire new information. 4. I browse the Internet every day. 5. I am an avid information seeker. 6. I am always actively looking for new information. 	Tang, Kacmar, & Buse-nitz (2012)
	Association and connection	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I see links between seemingly unrelated pieces of information. 2. I am good at “connecting dots.” 3. I often see connections between previously unconnected domains of information. 	
	Evaluation and judgement	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I have a gut feeling for potential opportunities. 2. I can distinguish between profitable opportunities and not-so-profitable opportunities. 3. I have a knack for telling high-value opportunities apart from low-value opportunities. 4. When facing multiple opportunities, I am able to select the good ones. 	
Entrepreneurial intention (5-point Likert)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. I am ready to do anything to be an entrepreneur 2. My professional goal is to become an entrepreneur 3. I will make every effort to start and run my own firm 4. I am determined to create a firm in the future 	Shirokova, Osiyevskyy, & Bogatyreva (2016)	

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 5. I have very seriously thought of starting a firm 6. I have the strong intention to start a firm someday 	
<p>Entrepreneurial behavior</p> <p>The index is measured on a scale from 0 (no activities) to 1 (full engagement in all listed start-up activities)</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Discussed product or business idea with potential customers 2. Collected information about markets or competitors, 3. Wrote a business plan 4. Started product/service development 5. Started marketing or promotion efforts 6. Purchased material, equipment or machinery for the business 7. Attempted to obtain external funding 8. Applied for a patent, copyright or trademark 9. Registered the company 10. Sold product or service 	

STUDY DESIGN/METHODOLOGY/APPROACH

The quantitative approach is employed in this study. The research process consists of 08 steps as follows:

Step 1 - Research topic: Entrepreneurship is receiving increasing attention from researchers, practitioners and policy makers because of its important roles in creating jobs, enhancing innovation, etc. It is suggested that entrepreneurship is about action (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006). Therefore, the topic of entrepreneurial action is of great interest for further research.

Step 2 - Literature Review: The author will conduct a systematic literature review on the topic of entrepreneurial action. The keywords “entrepreneurial action”, “entrepreneurial intention” and “entrepreneurial behaviour” are used to search for the related research papers on Google Scholar. These papers are then scanned and skimmed to identify what have been discussed on the topic and what are left undiscussed.

Step 3 - Research problem: More rigorous reading is conducted to identify research problems and research gaps. Recommendations from most recent literature review papers are taken into careful considerations.

The following gaps are identified:

- Given the importance of entrepreneurship, it is necessary to find out the mechanism fostering the journey from opportunity recognition to entrepreneurial action.
- Given the uncertain nature of entrepreneurship, empirical studies about the role of imagination in the transition from opportunity recognition to action is needed.

Step 4 - Research model and hypotheses: A research model is built based on established theories such as entrepreneurial action (McMullen & Shepherd, 2006), entrepreneurial imaginativeness (Kier & McMullen, 2018), TPB (Ajzen, 1990), entrepreneurial alertness (Tang et al., 2012). 04 hypotheses are developed based on foundational theories and results from previous studies.

Step 5 - Questionnaire: The measurement scales for all the factors in the model are identified. The measures are then modified to fit the context of the research with consultation from two experts in the field. The first draft is then tested by consulting some prospective respondents for their understanding. The final version will be used for a pilot study which includes about 30 samples to test the reliability and dimensionality. A questionnaire with the modified scales are used for the official study.

Step 6 - Data collection: In the official study, the random sampling is employed. As a result, questionnaires are delivered directly to respondents who participate in the Start-up Day event which is held every year in August. The acceptable sample should include 300 respondents.

Step 7 - Data analysis: AMOS20 is employed to analyse the data. The analysis steps include:

- Statistic description: Mean, Mode, Average, Standard Deviation
- Cronbach Alpha is conducted to test the reliability of the scale. If the reliability scores are within the range from 0.6 to 0.9, the scales would be acceptable.
- EFA is conducted to extract factors and test the face validity of the scale.
- CFA is used to test how well the measured variables represent the number of constructs.
- SEM is used to test the proposed hypotheses. The confidence level of 95% is employed to confirm the significance of those hypotheses. If significance is less than 0.05, the hypothesis is supported. Otherwise, the hypothesis is not supported.

Step 8 - Results Discussion and Recommendations: The results from analyses in step 7 are discussed. Limitations are stated and recommendations for practices and further research are suggested accordingly.

PRELIMINARY DISCUSSION

Base on literature review and the theory of planned behaviour, 04 hypotheses was developed to investigate the moderating role of entrepreneurial imaginativeness in the journey from opportunity recognition to entrepreneurial action. The findings promise to bring about interesting theoretical and practical contributions. However, it is inevitable that the study may have some limitations. First, the study only focuses on cognitive process of individual entrepreneurs, though new venture creation journey requires collective efforts of a new venture team. Second, self-report questionnaire will be employed as a tool to collect data, which may lead to self-serving bias.

CONCLUSION

There have been very few empirical studies investigating the role of imagination in entrepreneurship. This study will respond to the call for more empirical investigation about the role of imaginativeness on entrepreneurial action from McMullen et al. (2021). The study is an attempt to address two such gaps as (1) the mechanism fostering the journey from opportunity recognition to entrepreneurial action, and (2) the role of imagination in the transition from opportunity recognition to action. The findings from this study can reveal some managerial implications for entrepreneurship training institutions and entrepreneurship support systems to put more emphasis on developing the imagination skills of students and entrepreneurs.

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